

Field-testing of a variable-pitch, axial-flow marine current turbine with passive adaptive blades

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Advancements in marine current turbine technology remain hindered by reliability and cost. Turbines are designed around large peak loading conditions and, still, many deployments encounter catastrophic blade failure from underpredicting loads. Open water experimental testing helps to broaden our understanding of dynamic loading under conditions that are more representative of those seen during deployment and without the influence of confinement effects. Furthermore, strategies for load reduction can address both cost and reliability. Passive blade pitch control for axial-flow current turbines is attractive for its potential to significantly reduce peak rotor loads in above-rated flow conditions by shedding power at decreased angles of attack without the risk of failure modes introduced through active pitch mechanisms. In this study, we experimentally tested a 1-meter diameter axial-flow turbine in Lake Washington aboard *R/V Russell Davis Light*. Tests were performed using both passive adaptive blades and neutral, nonadaptive blades, to investigate passive adaptive blade performance and its potential role in passive blade pitch control strategies.

The passive adaptive blades, designed with a bend-twist coupling in the unidirectional carbon fiber layup, passively bend and feather in response to increased loading. The nonadaptive blades, with a balanced laminate and identical blade geometry, have no bend-twist coupling. The turbine, instrumented with six-axis force/torque sensors on the hub and one blade, was mounted to a gantry at the bow of the vessel and steered at vessel speeds 1.0 and 1.5 m/s to mimic naturally occurring river, ocean, and tidal currents. The nonadaptive blades were tested at 7 preset blade pitch angles, from 0° to 23°, and the experimental results were used to simulate an active blade pitch control strategy. Despite being designed without a bend-twist coupling, we observed with the nonadaptive blades that normalized thrust was still sensitive to changes in inflow at high tip-speed ratios (Fig. 1b). Calculations of the center of pressure on the blade, determined using the load cell measurements, suggest this may be due to the chordwise center of pressure moving towards the trailing edge of the blade as tip-speed ratio increases, producing a pitching moment and, therefore, twist deformation on both the nonadaptive and adaptive blades.

Compared to the nonadaptive blades, the passive adaptive blades reduced the normalized power and thrust for tip-speed ratios greater than 3 (Fig. 1). In 1.5 m/s flow, increases in tip-speed ratio beyond optimal were associated with further decreases in normalized thrust loads, which aligns with previous studies. While reduced thrust loads are desirable from a cost and manufacturing standpoint, the reduction in peak efficiency is impractical. The neutral blades achieve a higher peak efficiency (i.e., power coefficient), likely equivalent to the peak efficiency achieved with rigid blades based on our previous lab-scale passive adaptive blade studies. With this knowledge, the presented study shows increased potential for a passive method of blade pitch control that can offer notable load reductions relative to purely speed control strategies while achieving the same peak power output as conventional turbine blades.

Figure 1. (a) Power and (b) thrust coefficients as a function of tip-speed ratio for the adaptive and nonadaptive blades tested in 1.0 and 1.5 m/s flow.